

ACTION OF PREVOST'S REAGENT ON $\Delta^{9:10}$ -OCTALIN

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The action of silver benzoate-iodine complex on $\Delta^{9:10}$ -octalin has yielded 9-oxy- Δ^4 -octalin instead of the expected 9:10-glycol.

The silver benzoate-iodine complex is a useful reagent for the hydroxylation of an ethylenic linkage (Prevost *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196, 1129; 1933, 197, 1661; 1934, 198, 2264; 1937, 204, 989; Hershberg, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 351; Niemann and Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 227); the addition of the two hydroxyls is stereospecific and always *trans* (Wittcoff and Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3138; Slettinger and Dawson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 849). In connection with the preparation of decalin-9:10-diol (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 1) the action of Prevost's reagent on $\Delta^{9:10}$ -octalin was studied. The chief product surprisingly was found to be an olefinic alcohol; the expected *trans*-glycol (I) could not be isolated.

This product has been assigned the structure (II) on the basis of the following evidence: The elemental analysis indicates the formula $C_{10}H_{16}O$. The compound imparts a yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The substance is fairly labile and during distillation (at 5 mm.) is partially dehydrated to a conjugated diene (*vide infra*); this behaviour is consistent with the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated *tert.*-carbinol system, which is expected to be susceptible to ready dehydration (cf. Sukh Dev, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 325). Its infra-red spectrum had bands (relevant) indicated in Table I with the most likely assignments.

TABLE I

ν (cm. ⁻¹)	Assignment.	Reference.
(i) 3340 (S), Broad	O—H stretching; intermolecular hydrogen bonds.	Bellamy, "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen & Co. Ltd., London, 1954, p. 83.
(ii) 1650 (S)	C=C stretching.	Jones & Sandorfy in Weiss-berger's "Technique of Org. Chem.", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1956, Vol. 4, p. 369.
(iii) 840 (M)	C—H out-of-plane bending vibrations for a substituted olefine.	Jones & Sandorfy, <i>loc. cit.</i> , p. 382.

In the C—OH stretching frequency range (1000-1200), several peaks occur, out of which the doublet at 1055 and 1040 is the strongest, and taking into account the known shift (about 60 cm^{-1}) towards the lower frequencies caused by an olefinic linkage when present at the $\beta\gamma$ -position to a hydroxyl (Zeiss and Tsutsui, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 897), may possibly be assigned to the C—OH stretching vibrations of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated *tert.*-carbinol system. That this olefinic linkage is tri-substituted has further been confirmed by the end-absorption (Table II) in the ultraviolet region (Bladon *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2737; Halsall, *Chem & Ind.*, 1951, 867; Dawson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 590).

TABLE II
End-absorption.

λ .	ϵ .	ϵ for a tri-substituted ethylenic linkage (Bladon <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i>).
210 $m\mu$	4035	1400-4700
215	2480	600-3500
220	1570	250-1800
225	1335	...

All these data are consistent with the structure (II). A final confirmation of the structure (II) by catalytic hydrogenation to the known (III) (Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry, Amsterdam, 1950, Vol. 12B, p. 1378) could not be achieved, since the compound resisted hydrogenation over Pd—CaCO₃ catalyst in ethanol, and over Adams' catalyst in glacial acetic acid hydrogenolysis occurred as evidenced by no break at the stage of 1 mole hydrogen absorption.

The alcohol (II), as has been stated above, dehydrated partially during distillation to yield a diene which developed an orange-red colour with tetranitromethane and coupled with diazotised *p*-nitroaniline to furnish a red dye. The latter reaction is characteristic of conjugated dienes (Meyer, *Ber.*, 1919, 52, 1468; Fieser and Campbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 160; Bachman and Hatton, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 1513). The same hydrocarbon could be obtained readily by the dehydration of (II) over potassium bisulphate; the two products were shown to be identical by their ultraviolet spectra. The acid-catalysed dehydration of the alcohol (II) can theoretically lead to four dienes (IV, V, VI and VII). Since the product obtained has $\lambda_{\max}$ at 242 $m\mu$, the thermodynamically stabler structure (IV) is indicated; the calculated $\lambda_{\max}$

(IV)
(244 $m\mu$)

(V)
(282 $m\mu$)

(VI)
(234 $m\mu$)

(VII)
(273 $m\mu$)

values according to Woodward-Fieser rules (Dorfman, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 59) have been indicated below each structure. In confirmation of this structure, the diene on lithium-liquid ammonia-alcohol reduction furnished $\Delta^{9:10}$ -octalin. As expected of a heteroannular diene (Alder, "Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry", Interscience

Publishers, New York, 1948, p. 383; Bergmann and Hirsman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, **4**, 40), the compound furnishes a very poor yield of the maleic anhydride adduct, which is more likely to be derived from the homo-annular diene (V), produced under the reaction condition of the diene synthesis; such a behaviour is well recognised (Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, **20**, 1542; 1940, **23**, 1346; Goodway and West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2028).

Nametkin and Glagoleff (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 1570) have described a hexalin (IV and/or V) obtained by the dehydration of decalin-9:10-diol with dilute sulphuric acid at 150°; the physical data obtained for (IV) in the present work rule out this structure for the hexalin of Nametkin and Glagoleff. The 9:10-glycol could not be dehydrated by refluxing its benzene solution in the presence of iodine or *p*-toluenesulphonic acid; with formic acid (87%) at 100° the glycol yielded only a polymerised product..

There is sufficient evidence to show that the first step in the Prevost oxidation is the addition of the pseudo-halogen ($\overset{\Delta^-}{\text{R.CO.O}}-\overset{\Delta^+}{\text{Hal}}$) to the olefine (Waters in Gilman's "Organic Chemistry: An Advanced Treatise", John Wiley & Co., New York, 1953, Vol. IV, p. 1230) to give a halo-acyloxy derivative (Birckenbach *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1932, **65**, 1339; Bockemuller and Hoffmann, *Annalen*, 1935, **519**, 165; Uschakow and Techistow, *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 824; Halperin *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 623). The halogen atom, evidently, then undergoes a nucleophilic displacement by the anion (R.CO.O^-) with retention of configuration (Winstein *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2784, 2787; 1943, **65**, 2096; 1946, **68**, 118) to yield the *trans*-glycol derivative (cf. the preparation of *cis*-glycols by a modified Prevost oxidation: Ginsburg, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 5747; Barkley *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 5014). In the present investigation the expected intermediate

(VIII)

(VIII) has a tertiary iodo group in the axial conformation, which is coplanar with the axial hydrogen of the neighbouring methylene groups and so I_2 takes precedence; it is well established that tertiary halides are more susceptible to an elimination reaction (Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, p. 434) and that for a concerted bimolecular reaction, the four centres of importance must lie in one plane (Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027). It may be predicted from this result that in a rigid system containing a tetra-substituted ethylenic linkage, the Prevost oxidation would most likely lead to an unsaturated alcohol of the type (II), provided an axial hydrogen would be available for elimination.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were taken in ethanolic solution on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

Action of Silver Benzoate-iodine Complex on Δ^9 -¹⁰-Octalin.—In a litre flask, fitted with an adapter carrying a dropping funnel, a distillation head topped with a reflux condenser and a slip-seal joint for a Hershberg stirrer, was placed a mixture of dry silver benzoate (54.9 g., 0.24 M) and anhydrous benzene (250 c.c.), and with stirring benzene (ca 50 c.c.) was distilled off to secure perfect anhydrous conditions. The contents were allowed to cool to room temperature and a solution of iodine (25.5 g., 0.2 g. atom) in benzene (300 c.c.) was let in with stirring. To the yellowish complex, thus obtained, the octalin (13.6 g., 0.1 M) in benzene (30 c.c.) was introduced (10 mins.) and the reaction mixture was stirred and refluxed for 18 hours. The precipitated AgI was filtered off and washed with benzene (50 c.c. $\times$ 3). From the combined filtrates the solvent was flashed off (column) from a steam-bath under slight suction. The residue crystallised out on cooling and the crystals (a test portion recrystallised from benzene-petrol) were shown to be benzoic acid (m. p. and mixed m. p.). The residue was treated with KOH (20 g.) in ethanol (100 c.c.) containing water (20 c.c.) and refluxed for 2 hours. The product was diluted with water (500 c.c.), extracted with ether (60 c.c. $\times$ 4), washed with brine (50 c.c.) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated through a Vigreux column (12") carrying a total condensation type still-head to give fractions: (i) b. p. 60-62°/3mm, 3.5 g. (ii) b. p. 95-104°/3 mm, 8.5 g. and (iii) residue ca. 1 g.

Fraction (i) was rectified over sodium to furnish a hydrocarbon (3 g.), b. p. 80-84°/12 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5035, which was apparently a mixture of the starting material and the diene (V; *vide infra*), and from its η , was computed to contain about 75% of octalin; the presence of this hydrocarbon was established by the preparation of *trans*-9:10-dibromodecalin (Hückel *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1929, 474, 134), m. p. 137-58° (pet. ether), which was undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample.

The second fraction was observed to dehydrate on refractionation at 5 mm, and hence, the entire distillate (7.5 g., b. p. 69-107°/5 mm) was refractionated at 2 mm. The fractionation assembly was pretreated with warm aqueous Na_2CO_3 solution for a few hours to destroy any hydrogen ions on the glass surface. Following sub-fractions were thus obtained: (a) b. p. 60-61°/2 mm, n_D^{30} 1.5295, yield 3.0 g., this was identified as the diene (V) (*vide infra*). (b) b. p. 100-102°/2 mm, n_D^{30} 1.5140, yield 3.0 g., this product was characterised as 9-*oxy*- Δ^4 -octalin (II). It is a colorless thick liquid with the characteristic musty decalol odour and an analytical sample had n_D^{30} 1.5155, d_4^{20} 1.014, M_D 45.25 (calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$: $\overline{M}$: 45.05). (Found: C, 78.43; H, 10.59. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.94; H, 10.52%). Its infra-red spectrum was measured on a Perkin-Elmer double-beam instrument* on the pure liquid (smear) and had the following bands besides those recorded in Table I: 2900 (S; broad), 2640 (W), 1630 (M), 1440 (S), 1392 (S), 1350 (M), 1220 (S), 1285 (S), 1215 (M), 1180 (S), 1165 (S), 1140 (S), 1110 (M), 1077 (S), 1055 (S), 1040 (S), 1025 (S), 1005 (S), 985 (M), 960 (S), 945 (S), 910 (M), 880 (M).

The original fractionation residue (fraction iii above) was examined for the presence of the glycol (I). The residue was sublimed at 100°/35 mm and the sublimate (ca. 50 mg., wax) was crystallised from dilute acetone to afford white nodules (ca. 5mg.) of m. p. 171-73°, which were not studied further.

* Through the courtesy of Charanjit Rai

$\Delta^{4:8}$ -Hexalin (V).—The above-mentioned sub-fraction (a) was rectified over sodium to provide a colorless liquid, which was very susceptible to polymerisation, b. p. $81-82^\circ/9$ mm, η_{20}^{25} 1.5295, yield 2.5 g. The central cut had: η_{20}^{25} 1.5300, d_4^{25} 0.9358, M_D 44.23 (calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}$: $\frac{M}{2}$ 43.06; $E\Sigma_D$, 0.87); λ_{max} 242m μ (ϵ , 13670). (Found: C, 89.63; H, 10.33. $C_{10}H_{14}$ requires C, 89.55; H, 10.44%).

The olefinic alcohol (II) (500 mg.) was also dehydrated by its rapid (2 mins.) distillation at 7 mm over finely powdered fused $KHSO_4$ (25 mg.); the distillate was redistilled over $KHSO_4$ as before and the final material (b. p. $75-79^\circ/7$ mm) was rectified over sodium to yield the diene (300 mg.), b. p. $81-85^\circ/9$ mm, η_{20}^{25} 1.5297; λ_{max} 242m μ (ϵ , 12680).

Reduction of $\Delta^{4:8}$ -Hexalin to $\Delta^{9:10}$ -Octalin.—To a mixture of the above diene (500 mg.), ether (10 c.c.) and liquid ammonia (80 c.c.), placed in a three-necked flask, lithium shavings (500 mg.) were added (2 mins.) with stirring. The deep blue solution was stirred for 20 minutes and then treated with absolute ethanol (5 c.c.) during 15 minutes. After the evaporation of ammonia, the residue was diluted with ice-water (100 c.c.) and the product taken up in petroleum ether (20 c.c. $\times$ 2), washed with brine and dried over activated silica gel. Removal of the solvent and distillation yielded $\Delta^{9(10)}$ -octalin (350 mg.), b. p. $75^\circ/7$ mm, η_{20}^{25} 1.4370, which was characterised by the preparation of its *nitrosochloride*; blue prisms (acetone), m. p. 92° , mixed m. p. with an authentic sample (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*, 1954) was undepressed.

Action of Maleic Anhydride on $\Delta^{4:8}$ -Hexalin.—A mixture of the diene (1.0 g.), maleic anhydride (0.98 g.) and dry benzene (15 c.c.) was refluxed for 20 hours. The solvent was distilled off from the yellowish reaction mixture and the residue treated with an excess of aqueous Na_2CO_3 solution and worked up as described elsewhere (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 330). A lot of polymerised neutral portion was obtained and the dicarboxylic acid (120 mg.) was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture to give a white microcrystalline powder, m. p. $165-66^\circ$. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 7.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2%).

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